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Towards the multi-scale Kalman filtering of dynamic wake models: observing turbulent fluctuations and wake meandering

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Abstract.

When dynamic wake models are augmented with a Kalman filter, they can provide dynamic estimates of the turbine inflows. Such estimators –especially when implemented through readily available operational data– can support a variety of practical applications in wind farm operation and monitoring, power forecasting, and others. The present work represents a first step towards a multi-scale approach for the filtering of dynamic wake models, aimed at estimating both small-fast and large-slow scales in the flow. The small-fast scales are caused by flow turbulence, which in turn also causes wake meandering, whereas the large-slow ones represent the propagation of macroscopic changes of ambient conditions (e.g., the passing of a wind direction change front throughout a farm). It is argued that the small-fast-scale problem is more difficult to address, because of the lack of measurements between turbines, and it is therefore the focus of this paper. An ensemble Kalman filter is developed that, based exclusively on power measurements from the turbines, estimates small-fast changes in wind speed and wake position. CFD simulations are used to characterize the performance of the proposed approach. Results indicate that –notwithstanding the lack of measurements of the flow as it travels from one turbine to the other– the filter is still able to provide for reasonable estimates of the inflow at the downstream machine. Additionally, it is shown that the filter typically distinguishes between effects caused by ambient flow changes from those due to wake meandering.

1. Introduction

Open-loop wind farm control for power boosting is based on steady-state models of the flow around and within the plant [19]. Low computational cost surrogate (engineering) flow models are an integral part of any application of this technology. The steady nature of the models implies that propagation effects throughout the farm, wake meandering motions and unsteadiness in the ambient conditions are neglected.

However, beyond this already well-established approach, there are other applications that require accurate time-resolved predictions of local turbine inflow dynamics, as for example power boosting by model predictive control, power tracking, secondary frequency regulation, or short-time power forecasting [12, 4]. Dynamic wake models like FLORIDyn offer a low computational cost opportunity to tackle these problems [15, 21, 3, 13]. Such models provide a state-space description of the flow, where ambient and wake-describing conditions are advected downstream.

Unfortunately, due to the stochastic nature of the physical phenomena at play, open-loop dynamic wake models (probably irrespectively of their complexity) will in general never be able to faithfully capture all relevant flow dynamics with sufficient accuracy [6]. One classical approach to improve the accuracy of predictions is by the use of a Kalman filter, where measurements are used to correct the estimates provided by a dynamic model. In the framework of wake dynamics, this technique has already been successfully applied by exploiting flow measurements provided by lidars [9, 22]. Lidars are –however– not routinely deployed in commercial installations. Therefore, there is a need for methods that are able to provide dynamic flow estimates, relying only on actually available measurements. A first filtering correction of the flow based on turbine power measurements was presented in [14]. However, in that approach only the wind speed is corrected, which could lead to nonphysical results. In fact, for example, a change in power output could be caused by some factor other than a change in flow speed, such as the displacement of the wake or a change in wind direction. The method was therefore extended in [2], using a second Kalman filter to correct the local wind direction. The authors argue that wind speed and direction are correlated over different distances, which motivates the use of two separate filters.

The current study takes a slightly different point of view, but still with a focus on delivering methods that are implementable through measurements that are ready available on production machines (typical SCADA signals, possibly including loads on turbines equipped with the necessary sensors). The long-term goal of this research is to develop a comprehensive multi-scale approach for the estimation of the flow characteristics that affect the power capture and loading of wind turbines.

The spatio-temporal characteristics of the flow can be roughly split into: a) small-scale fast fluctuations, and b) larger-scale slower changes. The former small-fast fluctuations are caused by the turbulent nature of the flow, which in turn is responsible for the meandering of wakes. These scales are difficult to predict, because they take place as the flow travels from an upstream to a downstream wind turbine. Since no measurements are available in between the two machines (because only the turbine operational data is available), it is clear that providing an accurate reconstruction of such scales is very challenging [6]. On the other hand, the larger-slower scales correspond to flow structures of significant size or macroscopic changes in ambient conditions, for example a wind direction change front that propagates throughout a wind farm. When these scales are bigger than the typical distance among turbines, they are clearly easier to estimate with some accuracy. In fact, various affected turbines –through their response– provide simultaneous samples of such larger scales, easing their observation.

However, it should be realized that –in the end– both the slower and faster scales are important. For example, the slow change of wind direction over a farm is an essential piece of information for wind farm control, because wind direction dictates the path of wakes. However, also the faster scale fluctuations are important, because they dictate the oscillations of power that might prevent the accurate tracking of a power signal; additionally, they also dictate to a large extent the loading of wind turbines. Therefore, it is desirable to develop multi-scale approaches to filtering, which should be able to capture the dynamic changes that affect wind turbines across a broad range of scales.

In this paper, a further step in this direction is taken, considering the small-fast intra-turbine fluctuations of wind speed and wake position caused by turbulence and meandering. As argued above, this problem is harder than the observation of slow intra-plant wind direction changes. However, since also these slower scales are crucial for some applications, they will be incorporated in the present approach in a continuation of this research. Indeed, the study reported in [2] has shown that this is in fact possible. A further future addition to the present formulation is the idea of using a wake-affected turbine as a sensor, through the information provided by blade loads [27]. This concept has already been applied by [10] and [24], showing a good ability in determining the

vertical and lateral wake position at the impinged turbine in different environmental conditions.

Here an ensemble Kalman filter is developed to simultaneously correct the wake position as well as the ambient wind speed. To test the performance in a realistic scenario, corrections are purely based on power measurements. The analysis of the computed corrections, uncertainty parameters and statistics of the Kalman filter allow insight into the performance and intrinsic limitations of the approach, which –missing specific information on what happens between two turbines– cannot always provide for an exact reconstruction of the flow. Nonetheless, results indicate that even simple power measurements are able to provide reasonable short-fast scale estimates of the inflow at a wake-shaded wind turbine. In particular, through the use of CFD simulations, it appears that the proposed Kalman filter is typically able to distinguish with some confidence the effects caused by wake meandering from the ones caused by the turbulent fluctuations of the underlying flow field.

2. Methodology

2.1. Dynamic wake model

The implementation of the dynamic wake model loosely follows the original FLORIDyn formulation [15], as presented in greater detail in [6]. The main idea behind the model is to propagate flow quantities through observation points (OPs) in a state-space description. In steady-state wake modelling, it is a common assumption to describe the flow as the superposition of an undisturbed ambient background field with a wake field [25]. This split is retained here by using two different types of observation points in the dynamic model. Wake OPs contain flow quantities associated with the wake of a turbine, and are indicated with the subscript “ w ”. Ambient OPs represent quantities associated with the background flow, and are indicated with the subscript “ a ”. This separation allows for a distinct propagation speed of the two flow regimes. In fact, ambient conditions travel faster, while flow quantities associated with the wake move at a slower rate.

Firstly, for every turbine, a number N_w of wake OPs represent the bulk wake flow and define the wake centerline with locations $\mathbf{x}_w^k, \mathbf{y}_w^k \in \mathbb{R}^{N_w \times 1}$ in X - Y space at time step k . Currently, the model does not include vertical wake motions, i.e. the wake is assumed to stay at hub height, which eliminates the need for a z -coordinate. The wake OPs also contain the delayed turbine control states $\boldsymbol{\gamma}^k, \mathbf{a}^k \in \mathbb{R}^{N_w \times 1}$, which include yaw position and axial induction. The wake deficit magnitude and profile are calculated with the Gaussian wake model at every position [1]. For turbine T , the wake OPs model the downstream advection process as the following system of equations in state-space form

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_w \\ \mathbf{y}_w \end{bmatrix}_T^k = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A} & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{A} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_w \\ \mathbf{y}_w \end{bmatrix}_T^{k-1} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{B} & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{B} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_T \\ y_T \end{bmatrix}_T + \Delta t \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A} & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{A} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{U}_w \\ \mathbf{V}_w \end{bmatrix}_T^{k-1}, \quad (1)$$

where the time step is noted Δt and the turbine position coordinates are x_T, y_T . The components $\mathbf{U}_w, \mathbf{V}_w \in \mathbb{R}^{N_w \times 1}$, respectively acting in the x and y directions, indicate the effective transport velocity in the wake; here, the longitudinal component is slower than in the free stream, due to the speed deficit ΔU at each OP. Matrices \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} are defined as in the original study [15]: \mathbf{A} has a lower diagonal form, propagating states to the next OP, while the input matrix \mathbf{B} allows new states to enter the system at the first OP.

Secondly, a number N_a of ambient OPs with locations $\mathbf{x}_a^k, \mathbf{y}_a^k \in \mathbb{R}^{N_a \times 1}$ represent the undisturbed background field, originating in the same way at every turbine. These OPs contain the ambient wind speed and turbulence intensity $\mathbf{U}_a^k, \mathbf{V}_a^k, \mathbf{I}_a^k \in \mathbb{R}^{N_a \times 1}$, which are propagated to the next OP with

$$\mathbf{F}_a^k = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{F}_a^{k-1} + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{F}_{a,1}^k, \quad (2)$$

where F represents a generic ambient quantity (velocity component or turbulence intensity). The locations of the ambient OPs are updated in the same manner as the wake OPs, according to (1), albeit using the undisturbed wind speeds $\mathbf{U}_a, \mathbf{V}_a$ instead of $\mathbf{U}_w, \mathbf{V}_w$. As a consequence, the advection speed is higher in this case, and changes in ambient conditions propagate downstream faster than for the wake.

Two spatial mappings are performed at every iteration. First, the conditions from ambient OPs are transferred to the wake regime, represented by the wake OPs. This is necessary, as the effective wake transport velocity depends on the current state of the background flow. The transfer can be written synthetically as $\mathbf{F}_a^k \rightarrow \mathbf{F}_w^k$. This mapping is performed by linear interpolation based on separation distance. The second mapping is active only in waked conditions. Upon impingement, the background flow quantities from external ambient OPs are transferred to the waked turbine by an inverse distance weighting, which can be written as $\mathbf{F}_{a,\text{ext}} \rightarrow F_{a,1}$. Subsequently, the effective impinging velocity deficit is mapped to the respective rotor disk through spatial interpolation, i.e. $\Delta \mathbf{U}_{\text{ext}} \rightarrow \Delta U_1$. A depiction of the model, applied to the present two-turbine case study, is shown in figure 1b.

2.2. Kalman filter

This section provides a short overview of the Kalman filter that is used to correct, through measurements, the estimates provided by the state-space model. Due to the non-linear and stochastic nature of the problem, an ensemble Kalman filter (enKF) is used for this purpose [11], as also proposed in [9, 2]. This implementation avoids the need for calculating derivatives and the explicit advancement of the system covariance matrix \mathbf{P} . Rather, the process stochastics are represented by generating a number of model instantiations corresponding to perturbed state variables. The ensemble \mathbf{X} consists therefore of N_E state vectors \mathbf{x} :

$$\mathbf{X} = \begin{bmatrix} | & | & | & \dots & | \\ \mathbf{x}_1 & \mathbf{x}_2 & \mathbf{x}_3 & \dots & \mathbf{x}_{N_E} \\ | & | & | & \dots & | \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3)$$

The system covariance matrix is the sample covariance of the state vectors, i.e. $\mathbf{P} = \text{cov}(\mathbf{X})$. The whole ensemble is advanced forward in time as

$$\mathbf{X}^k = f(\mathbf{X}^{k-1}, \mathbf{u}^k), \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{u} are new flow quantities and turbine control states entering the system at the first OPs. For a simpler notation, superscript k is dropped from the following description of one Kalman filter iteration.

The inclusion of process noise is performed by perturbing each ensemble member. Noise is assumed to be normally distributed, i.e. $\mathbf{w} = \mathcal{N}(0, \mathbf{Q})$, where $\mathbf{Q} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_S \times N_S}$ is the noise covariance matrix, and N_S is the number of system states.

One possible implementation of process noise is based on adding an independent term onto each state, and in this case \mathbf{Q} takes a diagonal form [2]. Physically, however, the turbulent flow field between two turbines, which is responsible for disturbing the wake path, consists of spatially correlated fluctuations. Therefore, the current study assumes that process noise retains some correlation over distance. An exponential function, also used to describe turbulent autocorrelation [28], describes the decrease of covariance with separation distance between two states with indices i and j :

$$\sigma_{S,ij}^2 = \sigma_{S,ii}^2 \exp\left[-\frac{l_{ij}}{\Lambda}\right], \quad (5)$$

where σ_S^2 describes the variance of the added noise for a specific state type, e.g. ambient wind speed U_a . The symbol Λ indicates the integral length scale of the turbulent background field,

while l_{ij} is the separation distance between the corresponding OPs. This requires the update of \mathbf{Q} and the calculation of distances between all observation points at every iteration. To reduce computational cost, this is done for the average of the ensemble $\bar{\mathbf{X}}$.

In the following correction step, the measurements $\mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_{\text{obs}} \times 1}$ are perturbed with measurement noise $\mathbf{v} = \mathcal{N}(0, \mathbf{R})$, where \mathbf{R} is the measurement uncertainty matrix, to form an ensemble of observations $\mathbf{Z} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_{\text{obs}} \times N_E}$ [11]. The system output, which in the current study is only power, can in general be expressed by the nonlinear function $\mathbf{Y} = h(\mathbf{X})$. The system states are then connected to the system outputs through the ensemble statistics [2]. This is obtained through the state-to-output covariance matrix as well as the output covariance matrix, respectively defined as

$$\mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}} = 1/N_E [\mathbf{X} - \bar{\mathbf{X}}] [\mathbf{Y} - \bar{\mathbf{Y}}]^T, \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{Y}} = \text{cov}(\mathbf{Y}). \quad (7)$$

Finally, the Kalman gains are calculated according to

$$\mathbf{K} = \mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}} (\mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{Y}} + \mathbf{R})^{-1}, \quad (8)$$

which allows for updating the system state vector as

$$\mathbf{X}^* = \mathbf{X} + \mathbf{K} (\mathbf{Z} - \mathbf{Y}). \quad (9)$$

3. Simulation study

3.1. Case setup

A high-fidelity CFD simulation is used to test the proposed filtering approach, and characterize its performance. In previous studies, the CFD software was proven to simulate wake dynamics and wake interactions with sufficient accuracy for the scope of this work [31, 32]. The computational scenario consists of a cluster of two IEA 3.4 MW wind turbines [5], named $T1$ and $T2$, operating at a distance of 4 rotor diameters. The rotor diameter D is equal to 130 m and the turbine hub height z_h is 110 m. Typical partial wake impingement conditions were obtained by laterally staggering the wind turbines by half a diameter relatively to the mean incoming flow, similarly to previous work on wind farm control [7]. The inflow is obtained from a precursor simulation obtained in neutral atmospheric conditions. The average free stream flow field is characterised by a shear of 0.2 and a mean wind speed of 9.5 ms^{-1} at hub height. The turbulence intensity at hub height is 6%, with an integral length scale Λ of 82 m. The total simulation time was equal to 537 s.

Simulations are performed with the incompressible simulation tool SOWFA [8]. The actuator line method [29, 23] is used to model the blades, by directly coupling the CFD environment with the aeroservoelastic simulator FAST [18]. The projection of the aerodynamic forces onto the computational grid occurs via a standard Gaussian function approach. The domain is discretized using a structured Cartesian mesh consisting of approximately 13.5 million cells. The smallest cell size is 1 m in correspondence of the turbine rotors, and six refinement levels are applied to limit computational cost. The PISO algorithm [16] is used to handle the velocity-pressure coupling in the Navier-Stokes Equations, and turbulence is modeled with the large eddy simulation approach (LES) using the constant Smagorinsky method to model subgrid scales [26]. To eliminate the influence of small-scale turbulence and retain only the wake-displacing eddies, the flow field was filtered with a moving average. According to the suggestion of the dynamic wake meandering model [20], the filter window was selected as $T = 2D/\bar{U}$, where \bar{U} is the average wind speed at hub height. For illustration purposes, figure 1a shows the streamwise velocity at hub height at time equal to 177 s.

Figure 1. (a) Streamwise velocity of the LES simulation in the X - Y plane at time 177 s. The three stations used to identify the wake centerline at 1.5, 2.5 and 3.5 D are marked with a dashed line. (b) Dynamic wake model for the same time instant.

3.2. Meandering statistics

The meandering motions of the wake cause power fluctuations on the impinged turbine, especially in partial wake conditions as in the present layout [6]. This means that predicting the correct wake position is a key benchmark for the model and the corrective Kalman filter. For validation, the “true” wake location in the CFD simulation is identified with a tracking algorithm [30]. The algorithm approximates the wake deficit in the Z - Y cross-sectional plane by a two dimensional Gaussian distribution

$$\Delta U_{\text{Model}} = \frac{a}{2\pi\sigma_{cy}\sigma_{cz}} \exp \left[\frac{(y - y_{T1}) - \mu_{cy}}{2\sigma_{cy}^2} + \frac{((z - z_h) - \mu_{cz})^2}{2\sigma_{cz}^2} \right]. \quad (10)$$

The model equation contains five free parameters: a specifies the amplitude, σ_{cy} and σ_{cz} the lateral and vertical width, respectively, while the offset from the centerline is described by μ_{cy} and μ_{cz} , which is the quantity of primary interest here. A correlation between lateral and vertical width, i.e. a skewed wake is not considered. Figure 1a depicts the three downstream stations at 1.5, 2.5 and 3.5 D , where Z - Y planes of the streamwise velocity were extracted. Notice that the wake cannot be directly tracked at the 4 D station, where the waked turbine is located, due to its induction effect. The vertical shear in every Z - Y plane was removed with the average flow shear. The wake position was then obtained by fitting the profile expressed by (10) onto the CFD flow slices at every simulation time step.

A statistical evaluation of the computed wake offsets at the 3.5 D station reveals that the wake meanders in the lateral as well as in the vertical directions. The standard deviations in

the two directions, $\text{std}(\mu_{cy}) = 0.07 D$ and $\text{std}(\mu_{cz}) = 0.08 D$, are of a similar magnitude. This is probably due to the fact that, as the wake at this point has not propagated very far from the upstream turbine, the restraining effect played by the ground in the vertical direction has not yet influenced the vertical meandering motions [17]. Wake position and power production at the downstream turbine are clearly highly correlated, however the correlation for lateral wake motions, $r_{cy,P} = -0.71$, is higher than the one for the vertical one, $r_{cz,P} = -0.39$, although these statistics are probably affected by the relatively short duration of the simulation. Note that a negative displacement in the y -direction leads to a higher power output (cf. figure 1).

The dynamic wake model currently does not include vertical meandering motions. Therefore, the effects of vertical meandering on the observed power are compensated by the filter correcting the wake position in the y -direction. To account for this effect, the CFD-tracked wake is modified accordingly, i.e. shifting the wake at hub height while keeping its distance from turbine $T2$ constant, which gives

$$\mu_{cy}^* = d_y - \sqrt{(d_y - \mu_{cy})^2 + \mu_{cz}^2}, \quad (11)$$

where d_y is the lateral turbine separation. The adjusted wake position μ_{cy}^* will result in an overlap on $T2$ that is similar to that of a wake displaced by μ_{cy}, μ_{cz} .

3.3. Results

Focus of the present study is on the simultaneous observation of turbulent fluctuations of the streamwise ambient wind speed U_a , as well as meandering motions of the wake position x_w, y_w . Accordingly, the state space vector used in the Kalman filter equations (3-9) contains only these three state variables; for the upstream turbine, this writes

$$\mathbf{x}_{T1}^k = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_w \\ \mathbf{y}_w \\ \mathbf{U}_a \end{bmatrix}_{T1}^k. \quad (12)$$

The ensemble expressed by equation (3) therefore consists of state vectors of the form

$$\mathbf{x}^k = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_{T1} \\ \mathbf{x}_{T2} \end{bmatrix}^k. \quad (13)$$

The streamwise wind speed U_a at the upstream turbine is obtained through the turbine power production, yielding a rotor-equivalent wind speed (REWS). For the lateral wind speed V_a , the flow field is sampled in front of the upstream turbine. Only the power production of the downstream turbine is needed to feed the Kalman filter with measurements. The dynamic wake model was run with a timestep Δt equal to 5 s. 20 wake and ambient observation points span a length of ca. $5 D$, as shown in figure 1b.

The Z - Y flow field planes used for wake tracking were also used for the tuning of the wake model. The model calibration resulted in an adjusted wake expansion parameter $k_a = 0.33$. This value is smaller than typical values reported in the literature. This is to be expected, because literature values typically are calibrated based on longer term observations of the wake that include the effects of meandering, which in turn result in a wider wake [1]; on the other hand, here wake meandering is to some extent directly modelled, which results in a narrower shape of the wake. Wake deflection is neglected in the present study.

The measurement noise \mathbf{R} as well as the process noise \mathbf{Q} are regarded as tuning parameters, and were found with an iterative approach. The best results were obtained with the combination of measurement noise equal to $\sigma_{m,P} = 200$ kW, with process noise equal to $\sigma_x = \sigma_y = 6$ m for the x_w, y_w positions and $\sigma_U = 0.05$ ms⁻¹ for the background velocity. The use of 20 ambient

and wake OPs resulted in a total number of $N_S = 120$ states. A relatively high ensemble number $N_E = 200$ was used to minimize the statistical effects of a low sample number.

Table 1 reports some key performance indicators with and without Kalman filter. For additional comparison, the case was also run with a conventional steady Gaussian wake model without any propagation delays. In the table, the root mean square (RMS) error of the power prediction normalized by the turbine rated power is noted ϵ_P . The dynamic wake model without Kalman filter improves by 25% the predictive capabilities of the steady wake model, because it takes into account the downstream propagation of flow quantities. However, the open-loop nature of these predictions results in significant errors. The Kalman filter drastically improves on this situation, reducing the error by 63% compared to the steady wake model.

Table 1. Model performance

	Steady wake model	Dynamic wake model	Dynamic wake model with enKF
ϵ_P [-]	0.16	0.12	0.06
ϵ_{CL} [D]	0.13	0.07	0.04
r_{CL}	-0.04	0.69	0.92

The discrepancy in power prediction is the specific target of the Kalman filter, and therefore it is fully expected that this quantity will be drastically reduced. However, a smaller power error does not necessarily mean that the state variables have been correctly improved; in other words, an error in ambient flow speed might be compensated by a non-physical wake displacement, or viceversa. Therefore, a validity check of the results is attempted by looking at the tracked centerline. Figure 2 shows the position of the centerline obtained by tracking of the CFD results, compared to the centerlines of the three wake models. The initial transient of about 100 s is not shown in the graph.

The figure indicates that the prediction of the steady model –as expected– does not agree well with the CFD reference. This is due to the fact that changes in the inflow at the upstream turbine take immediate effect, as the model does not take propagation into account. The dynamic model without Kalman filter offers an improvement over the steady model through the inclusion of delays. However, it appears that significant deviations still do occur, especially between 200 and 400 s. This is likely due to meandering caused by large flow eddies that change the path of the wake between the two turbines, an effect which is not accounted for by the dynamic wake model. The system augmented with the Kalman filter shows an overall improved behavior, and exhibits a much better agreement with the reference centerline in the $200 < t < 400$ s interval. This seems to indicate that the corrections applied by the Kalman filter, notwithstanding the lack of information on what exactly happens to the wake as it travels between the two turbines, are in good agreement with the actual meandering motions of the wake and changes in the background flow.

Table 1 more precisely quantifies the visual impression offered by the figure, by reporting the RMS error ϵ_{CL} of the predicted centerline position, in addition to the position correlation factor r_{CL} with the CFD reference. Similarly to power, even for wake position the Kalman filter offers an improvement over the open-loop static and dynamic models. This confirms the validity of the corrections and the performance of the implemented ensemble framework.

4. Conclusions

The present study is a first step towards the development of a multi-scale Kalman filtering approach for dynamic wake models. Final goal of this effort is the development of a methodology that is able to predict both small-fast intra-turbine flow fluctuation and meandering motions, as

Figure 2. Centerlines of the wake released by the upstream turbine, measured at the downstream turbine, obtained from the tracking of the CFD results and from the three wake models.

well as large-slow macroscopic changes of the intra-plant flow. The implementation is based on a dynamic wake model loosely based on FLORIDyn, augmented by an ensemble Kalman filter, fed by operational power measurements.

A two-turbine wake interaction scenario served as the testing environment. CFD simulation provided the input for the dynamic wake model, as well as the ground truth for validation. Random turbulent motions in the flow field displace the wake, in turn causing a fluctuating power output at the downstream turbine. An open-loop dynamic wake model is unaware of changes to the flow happening between the two turbines, and therefore results in large errors. On the contrary, the proposed Kalman filter corrects the flow quantities in the vicinity of the downstream turbine using power measurements, resulting in much improved estimates.

Comparison with the CFD results illustrate the performance of the Kalman filter, and help confirm the physical validity of the corrections that it performs. As expected, results indicate that filtering improves power predictions at the downstream turbine. More importantly, a study of the wake centerline reveals that the Kalman filter updates are –to a large extent– physical, in the sense that they correlate well with the actual centerline movement observed in the CFD simulation.

The current verification scenario exploited the clear statistical correlation of wake location and power production, caused by the partial impingement of the wake on the downstream turbine. In other cases, e.g. in full wake conditions, it might not be possible to always clearly identify the direction where the wake should be re-positioned. In this case, additional measurements from a wake observer could be incorporated [27] in the present framework, an improvement that will be explored in a continuation of this work.

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